

TOWARDS ANIMAL-FREE GRAVITY RESEARCH: INTEGRATION OF ADVANCED CELLULAR CULTURE MODELS INTO ESA'S GEPAM PLATFORM

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Given that the ISS is scheduled to deorbit in 2030, ground-based facilities are essential for studying the biological effects of altered gravity in preparation for sustained human presence beyond Earth. They enable controlled exposure to hypergravity and simulated microgravity, as well as mechanistic studies of gravity-dependent biological processes.

Since 2020, the European Space Agency's Gravitational Experimental Platform for Animal Models (GEPAM) has provided a comprehensive infrastructure to study the effects of simulated microgravity, lunar and martian gravity, as well as hypergravity on aquatic and rodent models [1]. The platform includes multiple aquatic and rodent rotors for hypergravity exposure, as well as facilities to simulate microgravity, lunar and martian gravity using a random positioning machine (RPM) and hindlimb unloading systems to simulate microgravity on rodent models. GEPAM supports amphibian and fish in conventional environment, and murine models under specific pathogen-free conditions, with integrated facilities for sample preparation and state-of-the-art molecular and cellular analyses. The platform has been validated through collaborative studies, including altered gravity experiments on amphibian (*Xenopus laevis*) development and fish (*Dicentrarchus labrax*) embryogenesis. Aquatic species represent promising candidates for closed-loop life support and food production systems in a future lunar base [2].

To address emerging ethical, regulatory, and logistical constraints associated with animal experimentation, GEPAM has recently been expanded to include advanced *in vitro* systems. The rodent rotor has been modified to accommodate two CO₂-controlled incubators operating up to 5 g (Figure 1), enabling large cultures of adherent and suspension cells, as well as of three-dimensional models such as spheroids and organoids under various hypergravity levels. These types of samples can also be exposed to lunar, martian and microgravity conditions using GEPAM's RPM. These developments support the implementation of the 3Rs principle (Replacement, Reduction, Refinement) and provide scalable and reproducible models for mechanistic and translational studies.

The integration of advanced cellular and organoid-based models within GEPAM also aligns with

European and international regulatory initiatives promoting alternative experimental approaches [3]. Beyond academic research, GEPAM is positioned as an open and versatile platform for European collaborations, including partnerships with private companies and industrial stakeholders interested in gravity-related biotechnology, biomedical research, and space-relevant bioprocessing. By providing scalable and reproducible *in vitro* and *in vivo* models under controlled gravity conditions, GEPAM offers opportunities for the co-development of innovative technologies and translational research projects, thereby fostering public-private partnerships and accelerating the maturation of space life science applications. GEPAM also contributes to the development of biological knowledge and technologies required to sustain human health, food production, and life support systems for future lunar bases.

References:

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Figure 1: Large-diameter GEPAM rotor equipped with two CO₂-controlled incubators for exposing cell cultures, organotypic cultures, spheroids, and organoids up to 5 g.

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